

HISTORICAL REVIEW OF BRITISH AND AMERICAN ACCENT IN ENGLISH

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Annotatsiya

Today, the number of speakers of the American or British accent of the English language is growing. Therefore, it is natural for people to be interested in the history of these accents. The article also analyzes the history of the origin of British and American accents in English, the stages of their development, and their phonetic aspects and differences. Moreover, it highlights the process of origin of the standard pronunciation of Received Pronunciation (RP) formed in the territory of the United Kingdom and the general American pronunciation developed in the United States, and analyzes the main differences between British and American accents, such as sound pronunciation, intonation, intonation, and stress.

Keywords

British accent, American accent, Received Pronunciation (RP), General American, English history, phonetics, pronunciation norms, intonation

INTRODUCTION

If British and American accents are analyzed from a historical point of view, both accents originated from Old English and developed differently under the influence of historical processes. Migration, political changes, social stratification, and other languages have led to their diverse formation.

History of the origin of the British accent:

The British accent is an accent formed in the territory of the United Kingdom, the history of which dates back to the 5th century AD. During this period, Old English was founded by Anglo-Saxon tribes who migrated to the British Isles. Later, in 1066, the Normans conquered this tribe, and as a result, French strongly influenced English, causing changes in English pronunciation.

In the Middle Ages and later periods, different dialects were formed in different parts of England. As a result of London becoming the main center, the "standard" British pronunciation was formed. By the 19th and 20th centuries, a type of pronunciation called "Received Pronunciation (RP)" was considered an influential and formal speech model. Thus, the British accent emerged.

The origin of the American accent:

In the 17th century, English colonists entered the territory of the United States, and the American accent began to appear. Moreover, the language in America emerged as a result of a mixture of the pronunciation and vocabulary of Native American languages, as well as Spanish, French, German, and other immigrant languages. American linguists tried to simplify the spelling and pronunciation of English, and as a result, various differences arose and the concept of accent emerged.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Various studies have been conducted on the study of the history of the American and British accent in English, with particular attention paid to historical phonetics, sociolinguistics, and dialectology. Researchers emphasized that the formation of stress (accent) is caused by social, geographical, and historical factors.

One of the important sources in the study of the history of the British accent is John C. Wells' Accents of English (1982). In this three-volume study, pronunciation variants in British territory are covered in detail from phonological and historical perspectives. The author links the process of origin of Received Pronunciation, and its acceptance as a "standard pronunciation" in the 19th and 20th centuries, to social prestige and distinguishes it from regional dialects.

Another important work based on the historical development of Received Pronunciation is David Crystal's The Stories of English (2004). Crystal illuminates the evolution of the English language from ancient times to the present day and studies pronunciation changes in connection with social and political processes. He also emphasizes that the factors that had the greatest impact on pronunciation norms were the Industrial Revolution and urbanization processes in Great Britain.

The work of Albert C. Baugh and Thomas Cable "A History of the English Language" is of great importance in the formation of the American accent. According to the authors, the various regional dialects of the English population that migrated to North America in the 17th century formed the basis for the formation of the pronunciation of American English as a result of mixing in the new environment.

One of the scholars who deeply analyzed the phonological features of American English is William Labov. His work, The Atlas of North American English (2006), examines pronunciation differences in North America based on various studies. Labov substantiates with scientific evidence that the American accent, when divided into internal parts, also has significant territorial differences.

METHODOLOGY

In this article, various methods were used to study the process of historical formation of American and British accent in the English language. As an example, the research also uses historical-linguistic and comparative methods, relying mainly on the qualitative methodology.

1. Method of historical-linguistic analysis

One of the main methods that can fully illuminate the topic is the method of historical-linguistic analysis, in which the stages of formation of the British and American accent were studied from a diachronic (historical development) point of view. Through this stage, the phonetic changes of the English language in the 17th-20th centuries were analyzed and reviewed based on scientific sources. In addition, the method of comparative analysis is also considered one of the effective methods. Through this method, the method of comparative analysis was used to determine the phonetic and lexical differences between the aforementioned accents. The main differences in pronunciation, such as rhotic and non-rhotic features, length of vowels, pronunciation of diphthongs, spelling of words as they are pronounced, were compared and studied based on scientific literature. John C. Wells' *Accents of English* served as the main theoretical source in this process.

the sociolinguistic method was used to determine the influence of social factors on the formation of the accent. Within the framework of this approach, it was determined that the cause of changes in pronunciation is social stratification, migration, as well as the process of mutual communication of people.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This article is based on the study of the historical formation of the American and British accent through various methodological approaches. The results of the study can be studied through various methods, such as diachronic phonetic changes, regional and social differences, as well as the relationship between accents. As an example, through the section on historical development and diachronic changes, information was obtained that the formation of Received Pronunciation (RP) in the history of the British accent dates back to the late 19th and early 20th centuries. Moreover, according to the research results, Received Pronunciation was initially associated with social prestige through elite schools and universities and became popular as a standard pronunciation. According to research by John C. Wells, the phonologically significant simplification of RP compared to regional dialects leads to precise control over the length of vowel sounds and the pronunciation of diphthongs. Also, the development of the American accent was historically caused by settlers from Britain. As a result of the mixing of various dialects

of the English population that migrated to North America in the 17th and 18th centuries with the language of the new geographical environment, the General American (GA) variant was formed. According to the research of Albert C. Baugh and Thomas Cable, rhotic pronunciation (specific pronunciation of the r sound) is one of the most common methods in American English, and it differs from RP, since in RP the r sound is softly pronounced (non-rhotic) in many positions. Because RP in the British accent is characteristic of the upper social class, regional dialects are preserved in the working class and rural areas. In the American accent itself, there are also significant regional differences: the fact that the Northern, Southern, and Western dialects have their own vowel sounds and stress system proves our point. Also, there are various connections between the accents. According to the research results, the British and American accents have common historical roots, but the social, geographical, and political processes that took place in the 17th and 20th centuries led to their divergence. RP contributed to the standardization of the British accent, while GA contributed to the preservation of greater rhoticity and territorial division of the American accent.

CONCLUSION

According to the results of the analysis, historical roots and evolution, phonetic differences, social determinants, as well as regional differences can be the main reasons for this, and as a result, the English language has split into two - British and American accent.

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